
THE ROLE OF GENDER IN SHAPING THE ECONOMIC POLICIES AND OUTCOME NIGERIA IN FOCUS

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Abstract

Whenever the term "Gender" is mentioned, many readily attribute it to the womenfolk who in many societies are challenged and often put in a disadvantaged position to the men. In Nigeria, it is observed that the womanhood is reduced to a mere infidel and a second-class citizen hence, the commonality of general belief system that the best place for women is in the 'Kitchen'. This trend has brought about tremendous misrepresentation of women right at the level of the family down to the circular society. Women are therefore discriminated upon in most cases, from acquiring formal education, mistreated and perpetually kept as house- help. The low level of participation of women in Nigeria's politics is alarming and disturbing, hence hampers women from contributing their quota to the development of the State. Thus, the purported irrelevance associated with status of women in the society which has reduced an average woman to an inferior commodity. As a result, many women empowerment programs are being championed to cushion the effects of this subjugation on women. This paper attempts to look into gender and understand what has been in existence concerning gender roles, and how it shapes the economic policies and outcome in Nigeria. On this account, the paper adopted the qualitative research method, while utilizing textbooks, journals, newspapers, government publications, rules of proceedings and internet material. The study applied the functionalist approach and the theory of recognition by Axel Honneth in understanding, explanation and as well as germane predictions. The paper notes therefore, there is a specific role to play by both men and women to shape Nigeria economic policies to attain a more equitable outcome. More so, many African states are involved in the frontline discourse on the fight for gender equality through the adoption of public policies, aiming to improve the lives of women through social, economic, and political development. Based on the findings, the paper recommends that if both genders are correctly appreciated with each playing their role, not discriminating or demeaning any position, the resultant impact will be enormous, which will not only domesticate and advance economic progress and development it will further set the stage for attainment of sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Gender, Gender issues, Gender Roles, Gender Inequality

Introduction

Women constitute about half of the population of the Nigerian State and are known to play vital roles as mothers, producers, managers, community developers/organizers etc. Their contribution to the social and economic development of societies is also more than half as compared to that of men by virtue of their dual roles in the productive and reproductive spheres. The dominant trend has over the years assumed male superiority while women are seen as weak, subordinate and inferior and this has led to the emergence of specific initiatives such as the creation of the Family Support Program, the Family Economic Advancement Program, the Better Life for Rural Women Program and the formation of the Federal Ministry of Women Affairs in 1995. All these initiatives were targeted at intensifying the role of women in fostering societal developmental aims. Regrettably, this form of women's development program has been criticized for its failure to address and realize the real women's needs and wellbeing.

There is one form of inequality in virtually all human society, or the other, men and women do not have the same status in society, including the United States of America that is more favorable to women's rights. This is as a result of the fact that there are specific roles to be performed by every gender, and there are different ways by which these roles are rewarded; it is a fact that even the earth creation was not halted till a woman surfaced in the scene; therefore, human society is incomplete in the absence of female gender, failure to acknowledge women's roles will practically make social-political and social economic efforts practically impossible due to the unique functions embedded in each gender.

Policies on gender like the 'affirmative action in Nigeria structured in most cases with the idea of 'gender equity and 'women empowerment,' and to also lend voices to women's support and increased opportunities for women's health, education, employment, and to improve their required socio-economic conditions.

Gender role differences worldwide seem to be a natural phenomenon, which has brought about gaps in enjoying specific opportunities by men and women. Pointing out that this development has recently become worrisome to some clamoring, the female folk are given unhindered access to contribute to the development and be involved in policy-making. The aim of this paper therefore is to look at gender issues in Nigeria, particularly identify the issues of gender in policies and economy. Also, how gender sharpens the economic policies of Nigeria, and also to create a sense of value on each gender's roles, especially the female folk.

Literature Review

Gender

The concept of gender connotes the culturally and socially constructed roles with both men and women in society that gender as a social construct is learned, gender role play and judgment are also learned via socialization that existed before they were born. Several social attributes and privileges connected with being male and female are also issues relating to gender. Power relations in human society are defined by gender and also societal expectations, acceptable behaviors, and values at a particular time.

From the definition above, gender can be seen as a social construct, a socialization product where persons learned societal expectations as either males or females. Although it is seen as defining power relations, it is essential to note that what is valued and allowed in a man or a woman in a particular situation is determined by gender.

It is important to note the difference between sex and gender. Sex refers to the biological differences between male and female. For instance, the adult female has breast that can secrete milk to feed a baby but the adult male does not have. Gender roles differ from place to place and change with time. But sex roles are naturally fixed (Alamveabee, 2005).

In addition, Nkiru, Igbelina Igbokwe (2013) asserted that patriarchy is a set of social relations with material base which enables men to dominate women. The theory of patriarchy as postulated by Connell (1987) posited that the issue of masculinity has formed a critical part of gender order and cannot be understood separately from feminities which accompany them. This demonstrates the way social power held by men creates and sustains gender inequality. Connell stressed that the issue of gender inequality stems from the 'organized field of human practice and social relations' through which women are kept in subordinate positions to men (Connell, 1987 in Giddens, 2006). Connell does not agree with the notion that gender relations are fixed and static, she believes that they are the result of a continuous process and therefore subject to change and challenge. Connell could be considered a liberal feminist because her work dealt much with gender relations of inequality in society stating specifically the issue of power, labor and cathexis. To her 'gender relations are defined by patriarchal power ranging from the individual to institutional level, various types of masculinity and femininity are all arranged around a central premise: the dominance of men over women' (Connell, 1987 in Giddens, 2006, 463). This has been the situation of Nigerian women in all their years of struggle to gain access into the Nigerian political system. The term 'patriarchy' was fished up from an anthropological theory backwater and used to name systems of male power and oppression of women. Patriarchy had to be confronted by an autonomous women's movement, and the demand for the liberation of women was a revolutionary demand. Patriarchy promotes gender discrimination and depicts women as subordinates to men in the society, while feminism promotes liberation and freedom of women from such subordination. Women are always the greatest losers in Nigerian politics (Mohammed and Zaid, 2014). In 2015, records indicated an all-time low rate in women's participation elections compared to the previous ones. (Akpan, 2015: 1, and Gberiel, 2015: 4).

This is because of cultural and religious factors which portray women as subordinate to men. Unfortunately, the cultural and religious inclinations have been so ingrained in the minds of women that they consider themselves weak in all aspects of life. Thus, they are reluctant to contest for elections and withdraw due to fear, intimidation or lack of financial strength to contest for an election. Traditionally, women are inferior to men, as such as most women in Nigeria accept the perception of being inferior to men without question (Mohammed and Zaid, 2014). To sum it up one can say that political, economic, western gender stereotypes and traditional patriarchal institutions have all joined forces to deprive women of power. Nigeria is a male dominated society where power resides with men. Too often policies that promote and reinforce subordination of women are promoted in this male dominated society. The very low level of education among women and consequently, their low consciousness has made them

very vulnerable to the fraudulent manipulation of politicians and other dominant groups in the society. Although there are no current legal barriers to women's participation in politics, they are equally no enforceable laws that offer succor when women are discriminated against especially by administrative directives. The position of Igbokwe (2013), which is in line with Connell (1987), and Johannsdottir, (2009) concerning patriarchy which is mentioned earlier in this work stands out to be what goes on in most societies. Thus, their definition is clearly what happens in the Nigerian political world. Nigeria is a patriarchal society where women find it difficult to participate in political process because of several factors such as the dominance of men in the political system, sociocultural and religious, which makes it difficult for women to get into the system (Umukoro, 2014). The Nigerian constitution does not see a woman as a second class citizen, but the cultural practices does not give women the right to participate actively when it comes to decision making regarding them. The society does not permit women to contribute to its development economically, socially and politically (Samkange, 2001). For most feminists, women's ability to make choices and speak their minds has been proof of empowerment (Flood and Gill, 2010).

For centuries without end the status of women were perceived as none other than bearers of children and keepers of home. They were restrained from active participation in politics and other social activities. The typical attitude of the men towards women is that they can only be effective in domestic activities in the family and the assumption is that it is only men who know the problems in the country. Hence, women should be left alone to solve their home social problems while their husbands, parents and men solve public problems within the government. In the quest for their voice to be heard women must fight for their freedom and liberation in all facets of life. This is where liberal feminism comes into play.

Socio-cultural values play a significant role in shaping the level of women's participation in politics in Taraba State, Nigeria. Despite the constitutional provisions and international agreements promoting gender equality and women's rights, women continue to face significant barriers to entering and actively participating in politics due to deeply entrenched socio-cultural norms and values.

The patriarchal nature of Nigerian society, including Taraba State, often relegates women to the realm of the private sphere, where they are expected to focus on caregiving and domestic duties rather than engaging in public life and decision-making processes. Gender roles and expectations set by traditional values and cultural norms limit women's access to education, economic opportunities, and leadership positions, thereby reducing their likelihood of being involved in politics.

Furthermore, the prevalence of harmful practices such as child marriage, female genital mutilation, and domestic violence perpetuate gender inequalities and hinder women's ability to engage in political activities. These practices perpetuate harmful gender stereotypes, limiting women's autonomy and agency in political decision-making processes.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for this paper is drawn from functionalist theory and Axel Honneth, theory.

Some of those who contribute to this theory include Herbert Spencer, Emile Durkheim, and Talcott Parsons. The functionalist perspective typifies human society as a biological organism with various parts that harmoniously for its smooth functioning. In another light, Herbert Spenser's postulations' functionalist perspective views society as a multifaceted structure with different elements that must work in harmony to ensure the entire system's stability and survival

Axel Honneth, a leading critical theorist, emphasized understanding identity claims made by persons and social groups. Building on the necessary theory, he intends to address the violence perpetrated against those demands for recognition and the pathologies and injuries that arise from the petitioners. According to Honneth (1900/1995), people's involvement in political resistance is due to their violent experience to spontaneously assumed conception of justice and not because of certain abstract moral ideals, which means that people feel the need for recognition.

The issue of gender, especially with the rise of "perceived inequality" and its effect on the developmental process of Africa and Nigeria in particular, taking cognizance of the relationships that hitherto existed in pre-colonial Africa, can be said to have emerged from a perceived lack of recognition of the roles played by a set of gender which of course is the female folk. A critical look at the rise of feminism can be deduced that the outcry affected the female folk's hidden desire to be honored and 'accepted" for what and who they are.

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More specifically, and from Hegel's work, three forms of recognition are required by people. These are love, respect, and esteem these kinds of recognition are inter-subjectively attained and preserved (Mead's point of view). To relate with each other in these ways (and have self-confidence, self-respect, and self-esteem), individuals must obtain recognition from others.

Honneth, according to was criticized for making "recognition" look as though it is all that matters and placing much importance on recognition. However, it is evident that there is a silent craving for significance and recognition in all humans though it may not be all that matters; nevertheless, based on these criticisms, this paper merges the functionalist perspective with Honneth to make a further emphasis.

Gender Issues in Policies and Economy

The history of gender in Nigeria can be dated back through three specific eras: the pre-colonial era, the colonial era, and the post-colonial era (**Abdul et al. 2011**). During the pre-colonial era, Nigeria's political structure was purely monarchical. The nation was made up of diverse societies and kingdoms of which women participated actively in both the private and public spheres and influenced the socio-political scenes of the various regions (**Eniola 2018**). However, after the British amalgamation of the northern and southern protectorate, a colonial type of administration was formed in 1914. During this time, patrilineal and patriarchal kinship structures dominated Nigerian societies, which brought about the ideology that women should stay at home and take care of the family; during this

time, they were expected to engage in work considered complementary to men (**Aderemi 2019, p. 84**). These principles made a clear distinction between men and women both culturally and religiously in Nigerian society.

However, independence in 1960 ushered in a parliamentary system of government that lacked emphasis on gender. During this time, the national government dictated the lifestyles of women by endorsing the domesticity of women and the unwaged services provided by women to the family. Much of the legislation attempted to control women's sexuality, as well as fertility through defining their subordination (**Aderemi 2019, p. 83**). The division of labour along gender lines was more pronounced in the country's industries, as women in rural areas farmed and sold homemade products to support their families. Men in the south cultivated yams and women cultivate beans and cassava (**Aderemi 2019, p. 84**).

In 1999, Nigeria ushered in a democratic system of government, leading to a more realistic standard according to the world's assessment of democracy. The government at that time was led by Major General Olusegun Obasanjo, since then, and until the current time, Nigeria has experienced stability in its governance. In 2004, fiscal policies such as NEEDS, SEEDS, and LEEDS were enacted to solve issues of socioeconomics and sociocultural well-being among men and women across Nigeria. These programs were targeted at sustainable growth and poverty reduction, with the aim of empowering people and improving social service delivery, fostering economic growth in non-oil sectors, and enhancing effectiveness and efficiency in governance (**CBN 2005**).

In Nigerian society, gender roles are also manifested in social rights and entitlements in a form that denies women equal economic and political opportunities, especially the right of women to the ownership of land (**Ajala 2017**). The dispossession of women's right to inheritance, or ownership of land and other properties is one of the major barriers to the recognition of women's economic rights in Africa (**Techane 2017**) as lack of access to land, as a means of economic productivity can create women's vulnerability in over-coming poverty and violate their human rights. In many African societies, the issues of landed property ownership are often transferred within the family due to customary laws that often exclude women and girls from ownership and inheritance (**Techane 2017; Efobi et al. 2019**). In addition, traditional patrilineal advantages in Nigeria give preference to male children over inheritance (**Nwokocha 2007**). There are more words on issues concerning gender description and on issues affecting females rather than males in the policy documents. Education, which is access to basic primary and secondary education is an issue for female gender advancement.

Education

The national average of school children not in school in 2018 was 12.7 million, but presently, Nigeria has an increased rate of 14 million children not in school in 2020 (**Ogunnaike 2020**). As the gender gap widens, education is seen as a high priority area, with very large regional disparities across Nigeria. In the North, there is a very low school attendance rate of 35.6% of children in primary and early childhood education, therefore, only 53% of children have a clear daily attendance in school. Girls in the North have an attendance rate of 47.3–47.7%, which means that half of girls are not in school in the North. In the South, there are

schoolboys and girls not in school, which has created the high number of about 60% children not in school across Nigeria, and this will contribute to a high 60% illiterate adult population in the future. The low attendance of school children in Nigeria has been characterized by various factors, such as poverty, economic demands, and socio-cultural factors that hinder girls' education in policy documents.

Implementation

Public policy implementation is one of the significant issues facing Nigeria in its effort to achieve national development (**Ahmed and Dantata 2016**). Implementation in policy documents emphasizes the issues of the policy implementation gap. Poor policy implementation played a crucial role in re-enforcing gender-based discrimination in policy areas. For example, the weak implementation of gender-based policies, weak legal framework to protect and promote the welfare of women and children, and the lack of implementation principles in eliminating all forms of discrimination against women has been attributed to the structure of Nigerian legislation, which gives men more authority over the decision-making processes that affect women. There is a general lack of awareness and pervasive influence over issues concerning the importance of gender equality among policymakers. Policymakers are unable to manage their differences due to ethnic, cultural, and religious issues on national issues that affect their different groups due to institutional biases. The inconsistent and ineffectiveness of gender-responsive programmes and uncoordinated policy responses may be attributed to changes in governance, policy principles, corruption, and the low budget allocation of funds to solve policy issues.

Discrimination

For example, issues of gender discrimination in the access of women to education, and discrimination in land ownership against women were reportedly due to socio-cultural barriers that limit women from land ownership. In addition, sexual discrimination in employment against women is related to gender in the workplace, these especially affect women as regards employment recruitment, promotions, training, inadequate provision of maternity leave, health-care protection, and equal remuneration. Women also experience marginalisation in access to the use of technology and information regarding agricultural outputs and issues concerning climate change.

Impact of Women in Nigeria's Economy

Necessity-driven entrepreneurs are those who are pushed into starting businesses because they have no other source of income. Consequently, despite the high-level of female entrepreneurs relative to most countries, there are challenges and barriers in the country that limit women from scaling-up their businesses.

In the formal sector, very important results are emerging. At the lower levels in formal employment there is almost an even 50-50 split in the workplace between men and women. However, as both sexes climb up the corporate ladder, women begin to decline in representation on the senior leadership teams and at the board level.

As a result, women own only 20% of enterprises in the formal sector in Nigeria. Furthermore, only about 12% of Directors on corporate Boards of Directors are women.

And taken all together, at the rate Nigeria is changing on these critical dimensions, the Nigerian gender gap in the economy will only close in about 100 year.

Women are mainly involved in petty trading, selling wares in the market and street hawking in urban areas. According to statistics 78 % of women are mostly engaged in the informal sector, which are farming and petty trading. Despite this, their contribution is not commensurate monetarily. The women's unpaid labour is twice that of men, and its economic value is estimated to be up to 30% of the nation's Gross National product. Women self-advancement has been curtailed by the burden of reproduction, particularly in Nigeria with a very high birth rate as well as the cultural roles associated to women - role of child bearing, child rising and homemaking.

By the virtue of the population of Nigeria the potential female labour force is 50% but the actual value is 31%. The proportion of women in the formal sector is very minimal. This is noticeable in the industries and the civil services; statistics indicate that in the Federal Civil Service, which is the highest employer in the country, women are mostly found in the junior categories (Ajir, 2002).

Nigerian women, like their counterparts, around the world, face a lot of discrimination that limit their opportunities to develop their full potential on the basis of equality with men. They are far from enjoying equal rights in the labour market, due mainly to their domestic burden, low level of educational attainment, poverty, biases against women's employment in certain branches of the economy or types of work and discriminatory salary practices. In some establishments women are not allowed to get married or pregnant because it is thought that it will reduce their productivity and of course profit.

Impact of Women's Participation in Politics

The nature of politics is an important factor for the inclusion or exclusion of women in politics. Vicky Randall defines politics as an "articulation, or working out of relationships within an already given power structure", which is in contrast with the traditional view of politics that defines it as an activity, a conscious, deliberate participation in the process by which resources are allocated among citizens. This conception of politics restricts political activity only in public arena and the private sphere of family life is rendered as apolitical. This public-private dichotomy in traditional definition of politics is used to exclude women from public political sphere and even when women are brought into politics they are entered as mothers and wives.

The quest to understand the marginalization of women in political systems is the subject of many studies, some of which have been spearheaded by the Nigerian state. In 1986, for instance, a Political Bureau established by the General Ibrahim Babangida Administration to undertake a comprehensive review of Nigeria's political and socio-economic systems acknowledged a gender gap. It noted that 'full involvement of women in politics is one method of defending women's interests in society' The committee recommended the allocation of 5% of legislative seats to women at all levels of government, but the Babangida Administration rejected it. The issue is therefore not a lack of awareness about the

underrepresentation of women or the strategies needed to expand women's presence in the political space.

Women's aspiration to participate in governance is premised on the following ground; that women in Nigeria represent half of the population and hence should be allowed a fair share in decision-making and the governance of the country.

Secondly that all human beings are equal and women possess the same rights as men to participate in governance and public life. Women find it difficult to break into political positions because they are generally disadvantaged by gender ideology. Even educated women face hindrances. They encounter gender stereotypes that assign leadership to men, sexual assault, pay gaps and unpaid labour, including child care and housework, placing them at a disadvantage.

The various Nigerian constitutions guaranteed the rights of women to participate in active politics; however, the last decade has witnessed a relative increase in women's participation.

This is only when we measure increase in participation with certain standards like the number of women who vote in elections; the number of public offices held by women; number of women related policies implemented by government etc. Over the years, there has been a remarkable increase in women's participation in politics in Nigeria considering these standards, yet there is inherently a pronounced level of under representation of women in politics when compared with their male counterparts (Nkechi, 1996).

Every person shall be entitled to assemble freely and associate with other persons, and in particular he may form or belong to any political party, trade union or any other association for the protection of his interests: Provided that the provisions of this section shall not derogate from the powers conferred by this Constitution on the Independent National Electoral Commission with respect to political parties to which that Commission does not accord recognition.

Democratic governance is an entitlement conferred upon all citizens by law. The 1999 Nigerian constitution by virtue of Section 40 states that.

How Gender Sharpen the Economic Policies

Accelerating gender equality generates large economic gains. No society can develop sustainably without supporting opportunities, resources, and choices for men and women so that they have equal power to shape their own lives and contribute to their families, communities, and countries.

Access

Women are less likely than men to have access to financial institutions or have a bank account.

Women experience difficulties gaining access to resources that will be beneficial to their development. For example, access to finance is a problem for female business owners, as banks require collateral to access financial credit. In addition, women have limited access to contraceptives due to a lack of institutional mechanisms to make them available for free. Other factors limiting access to contraceptives are related to cultural, social, and religious

issues. For example, the permission of husbands to access services is essential; about 36.2% of women in Nigeria have an unmet need for access to contraceptives which requires the responsibility of all stakeholders in both government and NGOs for equality in all aspects of policy development to avoid the marginalization of gender to specific units or policies.

Women's Employment Central Driver of Inclusive Growth. On average across countries, long-run GDP per capita would be almost 20% higher if gender employment gaps were closed. Studies estimate economic gains in the order of \$5-6 trillion if women started and scaled new businesses at the same rate men do

When more women work, economies grow. Women's economic empowerment boosts productivity, increases economic diversification and income equality in addition to other positive development outcomes. For example, increasing the female employment rates in Nigeria could boost GDP by over 6 trillion, recognizing, however, that growth does not automatically lead to a reduction in gender-based inequality. Conversely, it is estimated that gender gaps cost the economy some 15% of GDP.

Investments, reforms, and interventions are needed to: strengthen and protect human capital, including by addressing gender-based financial violence boost assets, earnings and the productivity of women farmers, entrepreneurs, and businesses; expand female labor force participation and employment; and promote women's leadership, engagement and participation in decision making in communities, businesses, and the public sector.

Underlying Social norms that often constrain or enable gender equality

Increasing women's and girls' educational attainment contributes to women's economic empowerment and more inclusive economic growth. Increased educational attainment accounts for about 50% of the economic growth in Nigeria over the past 50 years. But, for the majority of women, significant gains in education have not translated into better labour market outcomes.

Women are more likely to be unemployed than men. In 2017, global unemployment rates for men and women stood at 5.5% and 6.2% respectively. This is projected to remain relatively unchanged going into 2022 and through 2023

Violence and harassment in the world of work affects women regardless of age, location, income or social status. The economic costs – a reflection of the human and social costs – to the global economy of discriminatory social institutions and violence against women is estimated to be approximately 12 billion annually.

Conclusion

The rights of women and female folks in the socio-economical and political space of Nigeria on her democratic agenda has been a matter of public debate and, hence attracts serious concerns by individuals, academic, public analysts and the wider international community as a whole. The plight of Nigerian women, like their counterparts in other parts of developed countries, have been characterized by lack of adequate representation, Lack of access to well-developed education and training systems for women's leadership in general; undue dominance of men in the economic and political scheme of things; Poverty or lack of money or resources; lopsided

political appointments and the general imbalances associated with very unjust treatment of the female citizens in its entirety.

There is no doubt that this trend negates the collective interests of human fundamental rights and the rights of equality, freedom and personal dignity of women in society. Therefore, in order to address the women question and transform gender relations, there is the need to challenge gender issues in all its manifestations in domestic production, paid employment, culture and religion, sexuality, male violence and the State; and specifically promote women's rights.

Recommendation

Democracy anywhere in the world is the prerogative of the people. This is because sovereignty they say, belongs to the people (women inclusive). It is therefore important that the act of governance should be diversified to capture the interest of women through adequate representation. Societal obstacles of religion, tradition and other obnoxious beliefs must be broken, women should not be domesticated, they have to enjoy right to work and associated benefits as men.

More so, if both genders are correctly appreciated with each playing their role, not discriminating or demeaning any position, the resultant impact will be enormous, which will not only domesticate and advance economic progress and development it will further set the stage for attainment of sustainable economic development in Nigeria.

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